

RAMI: Radiomics Predictive Model of Myocardial Infarction and Microvascular Obstruction

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Background

Late gadolinium Enhancement (LGE) has become the reference standard for assessing myocardial infarction (MI) and viability, which can be used to guide revascularization decisions [1-4]. LGE can also predict functional recovery after revascularization therapy. In addition, dark no-reflow regions (or microvascular obstruction) can appear within LGE-enhanced regions, indicating that blood flow remains inadequate post-revascularization. These no-reflow regions have been associated with worse clinical outcomes [5]. Segmentation and classification methods have been proposed to automatically detect scar tissue in LGE images. However, these mainly focus on regions of LGE uptake and do not address areas of no-reflow [6,7]. Moreover, automated segmentation is challenging due to high variability across subjects, potential lack of contrast between myocardial scar tissue and adjacent blood pool, complex LGE-enhancement patterns, and poor image quality. Radiomics has become popular in medical imaging for automatic quantitative feature extraction [8,9], which can potentially help identify diseased tissues. The obtained features can describe shape, first-, second-, and higher-order statistics. Shape features reflect morphological characteristics (e.g., volume, maximum surface), first-order features describe intensity distributions (e.g., mean, standard deviation), second-order features provide texture information to measure the spatial arrangement of pixel intensities (e.g., gray-level co-occurrence matrix), and high-order features analyze the spatial relationships by applying filters or mathematical transforms (e.g., wavelet). Here, we propose two radiomics models based on LGE features to improve MI diagnosis and detect no-reflow.

Methods

Clinical data: 100 patient datasets (33 normal cases and 67 pathological cases, including 40 with no-reflow) from the EMIDEC T1-weighted Phase Sensitive Inversion Recovery (PSIR) dataset [10], and corresponding segmentation labels, were used. Data were obtained using 1.5T and 3T MRI scanners (Siemens, Erlangen, Germany) and consisted of 5-10 short-axis slices, with in-plane resolution between $1.25 \times 1.25 \text{ mm}^2$ and $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ and slice thickness of 8 mm. For each image, segmentations of the healthy myocardium, myocardial infarction, and no-reflow were available. The dataset was split into training (70%), used to optimize the models through a 4-fold cross-validation process, and held-out test (30%) sets while maintaining stratified proportions.

Model 1 | RAMI: The first RAdiomics model for Myocardial Infarction detection, RAMI, was constructed using logistic regression with elastic net regularization and image features extracted from myocardium segmentation.

Model 2 | RAMI-NOR: The second model, RAMI-NOR, was developed using a random forest that specifically targeted the identification of MI with NO-Reflow by considering image features extracted from MI segmentation.

SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) analysis was used to explain model outputs. Figure 1 shows the models flowchart.

Results

RAMI, the proposed model for automated MI detection, exhibited excellent performance, achieving an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.99 ± 0.02 and 0.95 on the cross-validation and held-out test, respectively. RAMI achieved a remarkable sensitivity of $100\% \pm 0\%$ on both sets and specificities of $90\% \pm 17\%$ and 100% , respectively. RAMI-NOR, the model designed to identify MI cases with no-reflow, yielded lower AUC values of 0.76 ± 0.10 on the cross-validation and 0.71 on the held-out test. Regarding sensitivity, this model achieved $83\% \pm 17\%$ on the cross-validation and 70% on the held-out test. Specificity values were $79\% \pm 27\%$ and 73% , respectively. Figures 2&3 show the confusion matrices and SHAP plots for RAMI and RAMI-NOR. Figure 4 displays representative cases featuring segmentations and obtained radiomics maps. For RAMI, the most important feature was the correlation feature from gray-level co-occurrence matrix (glcm). The Maximal Correlation Coefficient (MCC) feature achieved the best performance in discriminating between cases with and without non-reflow.

Conclusions

Two radiomics models based on LGE features were proposed to automatically assess the presence of myocardial infarction (RAMI) and microvascular obstruction (RAMI-NOR). RAMI, a highly accurate logistic regression model, showed great potential to automatically distinguish normal and pathological cases based on LGE radiomics features. RAMI-NOR has shown promise for assessing MI cases with no-reflow, but still requires further fine-tuning or exploration of alternative deep learning-based methods to address the more complex cases effectively.

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Figure 1. Flowchart of RAMI and RAMI-NOR, radiomics models for Myocardial Infarction (MI) and no-reflow detection, respectively. For **RAMI**, the MI diagnosis model, myocardium segmentations were used to extract radiomics features, which were then used to train a logistic regression model. The **RAMI-NOR** model relied on radiomics features extracted from segmentations of the MI area to identify cases with no-reflow. To enhance model explainability, SHAP analysis was used to obtain the most important features of each model. Then, radiomics feature maps of those features were generated.

Figure 2. RAMI Model confusion matrix and SHAP analysis results for the held-out test dataset. **(A)** Confusion matrix of the RAMI model on the held-out test dataset (0 – normal case; 1 – myocardial infarction, MI); **(B)** RAMI model SHAP beeswarm plot of feature importance. The most important feature was the correlation feature from gray-level co-occurrence matrix (glcm). Other glcm, gray-level dependence matrix (gldm), shape, and first-order features were among the most important features.

Figure 3. RAMI-NOR Model confusion matrix and SHAP analysis results for the held-out test dataset. **(A)** Confusion matrix of the RAMI-NOR model on the held-out test dataset (0 – MI without no-reflow; 1 – MI with no-reflow); **(B)** RAMI-NOR model SHAP summary plot of feature impact on the model output. The feature with most impact on the model output was the Maximal Correlation Coefficient, MCC, from the gray-level co-occurrence matrix (glcm). Other glcm, gray-level dependence matrix (gldm), gray-level run-length matrix (glrlm), shape, and first-order features were among the features impacting the model the most.

Figure 4. (Column 1) LGE images of 3 representative cases: normal, myocardial infarction (MI) only and MI with no-reflow; (Column 2) Corresponding segmentations; (Column 3) Gray-level co-occurrence matrix (glcm) correlation radiomics maps. MI cases have less purple and more green areas (lower values) than the normal case. (Column 4) glcm correlation and Maximal Correlation Coefficient (MCC) radiomics maps. For the MI case, the MI area is mainly purple and blue, while the MI + no-reflow region is mainly red (lower values), showing the importance of MCC for detecting no-reflow.

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